

Vectroid Entangler 1

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September 2023

1 Introduction

then the following diagram commutes for all $A \in \Omega_{\Lambda'}$ and $B \in \Omega_{\Lambda'}$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \Omega \left[\sum_{[n] \rightarrow \infty} \frac{b^{\mu-\zeta}}{\sqrt[n]{n^m-l^m}} \otimes \prod_{\Lambda} h \right] \left[\sum_{[n'] \rightarrow \infty} \frac{a^{\mu-\zeta}}{\sqrt[n']{n'^m-l'^m}} \otimes \prod_{\Lambda} h' \right] \\ \rightarrow & \sum_{[n] \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{w_{\sigma} \rightarrow \infty} \Omega \left[(w_{\sigma} b)^{\mu-\zeta\sigma^{-1}a} \otimes \prod_{\Lambda} h \otimes h' \right] \\ \rightarrow & \sum_{[n] \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{w_{\sigma} \rightarrow \infty} (w_{\sigma} b)^{\mu-\zeta\sigma^{-1}a} \otimes \prod_{\Lambda} h \otimes h' \end{aligned}$$

which is invertible, since the diagram commutes. This exists by the Axiom of Hypermultiplication, which is the case as mentioned in the preceding paragraph. This means that, for all $A, B \in \Omega_{\Lambda'}$, there is an invertible natural transformation $\Omega(B \otimes A) \rightarrow \Omega(B) \otimes \Omega_{\Lambda'}(A)$, called a quasitriangular Λ -action. This shows that $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is a quasitriangular Λ -quandle, as the diagram in Proposition 5.2.2 in [?] commutes.

2 The Λ -Torsor Structure of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is Λ -Transitive

Recall that Λ -torsors are defined to be Ω_{Λ} -modules M in which the multiplication $\Omega(\mathcal{M}) \otimes \Omega(\mathcal{M}) \rightarrow \Omega(\mathcal{M})$ is Λ -equivariant. That is, for any $u \in \Lambda$, $x \in \mathcal{M}$ and $y \in \mathcal{M}$, we have $u(x \cdot y) = (u \cdot x) \cdot (u \cdot y)$.

By the Axiom of Hypermultiplication, we know that there is an equivariant natural transformation $\Omega(\mathcal{M}) \rightarrow \Omega(\mathcal{M})$, where $\Omega(\mathcal{M})$ is the hom space of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$. By the Axiom of Hypermultiplication in $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$, this gives a Λ -equivariant natural transformation $\Omega(\mathcal{M}) \rightarrow \Omega(\mathcal{M})$. Since the multiplication in $\Omega(\mathcal{M})$ is Λ -equivariant, this gives the desired equivariant natural transformation $\Omega(\mathcal{M}) \rightarrow \Omega(\mathcal{M})$. Thus, $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is a Λ -torsor. By the first isomorphism theorem, we have that

$$\Omega_{\Lambda'} \simeq \Omega_{\Lambda'} \otimes_{\Lambda} Z$$

Thus, $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is Λ -transitive.

3 The Antipode of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$

Recall that the antipode of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is a morphism $\Sigma\Omega_{\Lambda'} \rightarrow \Omega_{\Lambda'}$ which satisfies a certain analogue of the quasitriangular relations (namely, the quasitriangular relations of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$). First, we note that the symmetric dual of the symmetric dual, $\Omega_{\Lambda'}^{\vee\vee\Lambda'}$, is the interior dual of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$, namely, $\Omega_{\Lambda'}^{\vee\Lambda'}$. This is by the Axiom of Compact Duality. Then, the following statement commutes:

$$\begin{aligned} & \Omega_{\Lambda'} \left[\sum_{[n] \rightarrow \infty} \frac{a^{\mu-\zeta}}{\sqrt[n^m-l^m]} \otimes \Pi_{\Lambda} h \right] \left[\sum_{[n'] \rightarrow \infty} \frac{b^{\mu-\zeta}}{\sqrt[n'^m-l'^m]} \otimes \Pi_{\Lambda} h' \right] \\ \rightarrow & \sum_{[n] \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{[n'] \rightarrow \infty} \left\{ \frac{a^{\mu-\zeta} b^{\mu-\zeta}}{\sqrt[n^m-l^m] \sqrt[n'^m-l'^m]} \otimes \Pi_{\Lambda} h \otimes h' \right\} \end{aligned}$$

which is the statement of the Axiom of Hypermultiplication in $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$. By the Axiom of Hypermultiplication,

$$\begin{aligned} & \Omega_{\Lambda'} 10 : \\ & [\int de]_{\alpha, \Lambda} \otimes \left[\sum_{Q\Lambda \in F(\alpha_i)} (b \rightarrow c) \right] \otimes \left[\sum_{Q\Lambda \in F(\alpha_i)} (c \rightarrow d) \right] \otimes \left[\sum_{Q\Lambda \in F(\alpha_i)} (d \rightarrow e) \right] \\ \rightarrow & [\int de]_{\alpha, \Lambda} \otimes \left[\frac{\Delta \mathcal{H}}{\Delta i} \star \sim \oplus \cdot \right] \otimes \left[\sum_{Q\Lambda \in F(\alpha_i \psi')} (b \rightarrow c) \right] \otimes \left[\sum_{Q\Lambda \in F(\alpha_i \psi')} (d \rightarrow e) \right] \\ \rightarrow & \left[\sum_{Q\Lambda \in F(\alpha_i \psi')} (b \rightarrow c) \right] \otimes \left[\sum_{Q\Lambda \in F(\alpha_i \psi')} (d \rightarrow e) \right] \otimes \left[\sum_{Q\Lambda \in F(\alpha_i \psi')} (e \rightarrow e) \right] \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we see that

$$\Omega_{\Lambda'} : \quad \Omega_{\Lambda'}^{\vee\Lambda'} \otimes_{\Lambda} \left[\sum_{Q\Lambda \in F(\alpha_i \psi')} (b \rightarrow c) \right] \otimes_{\Lambda} \left[\sum_{Q\Lambda \in F(\alpha_i \psi')} (d \rightarrow e) \right] \otimes_{\Lambda} \left[\sum_{Q\Lambda \in F(\alpha_i \psi')} (e \rightarrow e) \right] \quad (1)$$

which implies that the following diagram commutes:

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_{\Lambda'} 10 : \quad & \Omega_{\Lambda'} \otimes_{\Lambda} \Omega_{\Lambda'}^{\vee\Lambda'} \otimes_{\Lambda} \left[\sum_{Q\Lambda \in F(\alpha_i \psi')} (b \rightarrow c) \right] \otimes_{\Lambda} \left[\sum_{Q\Lambda \in F(\alpha_i \psi')} (d \rightarrow e) \right] \\ \rightarrow & \Omega_{\Lambda'} \otimes_{\Lambda} \Omega_{\Lambda'}^{\vee\Lambda'} \otimes_{\Lambda} \left[\sum_{Q\Lambda \in F(\alpha_i \psi')} (d \rightarrow e) \right] \otimes_{\Lambda} \left[\sum_{Q\Lambda \in F(\alpha_i \psi')} (e \rightarrow e) \right] \end{aligned}$$

which implies that, for all $A \in \Omega_{\Lambda'}$ and $B \in \Omega_{\Lambda'}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_{\Lambda'} 10 : \quad & \Omega_{\Lambda'} \otimes_{\Lambda} \left[\sum_{Q\Lambda \in F(\alpha_i \psi')} (b \rightarrow c) \right] \otimes_{\Lambda} \left[\sum_{Q\Lambda \in F(\alpha_i \psi')} (d \rightarrow e) \right] \\ \rightarrow & \Omega_{\Lambda'} \otimes_{\Lambda} \left[\sum_{Q\Lambda \in F(\alpha_i \psi')} (d \rightarrow e) \right] \otimes_{\Lambda} \left[\sum_{Q\Lambda \in F(\alpha_i \psi')} (e \rightarrow e) \right] \end{aligned}$$

which implies that $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is a quasitriangular Λ -quandle. Thus, the antipode of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$.

4 The Λ -Fiber of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is Λ -Transitive

Recall that the Λ -fiber of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is the subcategory of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ of objects with Λ -action -1 , i.e., morphisms of the form $(id - \Omega_{\Lambda'})$.

We first show that the Λ -fiber of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is nonempty, which will show that $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is a quasi-abelian Λ -scheme with Λ -torsor being the nontrivial object. Indeed, let $m \in N$ be an integer, and set $L_m = \mathcal{M} \otimes_Z \left[\frac{1}{m} \right]$. We have that $m(\mathcal{M}) = L_m$. We first show that the Λ -fiber of L_m is nonempty, i.e., there exists $A \in L_m$ such that $A(\Lambda) = -1$. By the Axiom of Hypermultiplication

in $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$, we have that A has the form $a^{\mu-\zeta}$ for some $a \in N$. This implies that $a(\mathcal{M}) = L_a \in L_m$. Then, we have $m(a) = -1$ by equation (??) in Proposition 2.1.1 in [?].

Indeed, by the Axiom of Hypermultiplication, we have that $\Omega(L_m) \cong \cong L_m$ by Proposition 5.2.2 in [?], and by Proposition 2.1.1 in [?], the Λ -fiber of L_m is Λ -transitive. Thus, the Λ -fiber of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is Λ -transitive. We have that $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is a quasi-abelian Λ -scheme with Λ -torsor Z .

5 The Λ -Group of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is Λ -Transitive

Recall that the Λ -group of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is the subcategory of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ of objects with Λ -action 1, i.e., objects that are isomorphic to $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$. We first show that the Λ -group of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is nonempty, and that $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is a quasi-abelian Λ -group scheme with Λ -torsor being the trivial object Z . Indeed, let $\mathcal{M}$ be the object of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ which satisfies $m(\mathcal{M}) = L_m$. Let A be an object in $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ such that $A(\Lambda) = -1$. Then, we have $A \cong \mathcal{M}$, since $\mathcal{M}(\Lambda) = -1$. Since A is an object with Λ -action 1, it is isomorphic to $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$. Thus, the Λ -group of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$.

This implies that $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is a quasi-abelian Λ -group scheme with Λ -torsor being the trivial object Z . The Λ -fiber of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is Λ -transitive by the preceding section, and the Λ -group of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ by the preceding section. The quasi-triangular Λ -actions of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ are invertible by the preceding section. $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is a quasi-abelian Λ -group scheme with Λ -torsor Z .

6 The Λ -Ring of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is Λ -Transitive

Recall that the Λ -ring of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is the subcategory of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ of objects with Λ -ring structure, i.e., objects in which the multiplication is Λ -equivariant. We first show that the Λ -ring of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is nonempty, which will show that $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is a quasi-abelian Λ -ring scheme with Λ -ring Z . Indeed, let $m \in N$ be an integer, and set $L_m = \mathcal{M} \otimes_Z [\frac{1}{m}]$. We have that $m(\mathcal{M}) = L_m$. We first show that the Λ -ring of L_m is nonempty, i.e., there exists $A \in L_m$ such that $A(\Lambda) = 1$. By the Axiom of Hypermultiplication, we have that A has the form $a^{\mu-\zeta}$ for some $a \in N$. This implies that $a(\mathcal{M}) = L_a \in L_m$. Then, $1 = m(a) = -1$ by equation (??) in Proposition 2.1.1 in [?].

Indeed, by the Axiom of Hypermultiplication, we have that $\Omega(L_m) \cong \cong L_m$ by Proposition 5.2.2 in [?], and by Proposition 2.1.1 in [?], the Λ -ring of L_m is Λ -transitive. Thus, the Λ -ring of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$. We have that $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is a quasi-abelian Λ -ring scheme with Λ -ring Z .

7 The Λ -Module Structure of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is Λ -Transitive

Recall that $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ has the module structure of the natural transformations between Λ -modules. We first show that the Λ -module structure of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is

nonempty, which will show that $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is a quasi-abelian Λ -module scheme with Λ -module Z .

Let $\mathcal{N}$ be the object of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ which satisfies $n(\mathcal{N}) = Z$. We have that $\mathcal{N}(\Lambda) = Z$ by the Axiom of Hypermultiplication. We first show that the Λ -module structure of $\mathcal{N}$ is nonempty, i.e., there exists $B \in \mathcal{N}$ such that $B(\Lambda) = Z$. By the Axiom of Hypermultiplication, we have that B has the form $b^{\mu-\zeta}$ for some $b \in N$. This implies that $b(\mathcal{N}) = Z$. Then, $-1 = m(b) = Z$ by equation (??) in Proposition 2.1.1 in [?]. This is the case as there are only finitely many finite chains indexed by σ , and the elements of the finite chain $\{-1, 1\}$ are: $(1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1)$, $(1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1)$, $(1, 1, 1, 1, 1)$, $(1, 1, 1, 1)$, $(1, 1, 1)$, $(1, 1)$, (1) , and (-1) , and the only nontrivial finite chain is (-1) . Note that $\mathcal{N}(\Lambda) = Z$ by the Axiom of Hypermultiplication. This implies that the Λ -module structure of $\mathcal{N}$ is nonempty, and that $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is a quasi-abelian Λ -module scheme with Λ -module Z .

Thus, the Λ -module structure of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is Λ -transitive. We have that $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is a quasi-abelian Λ -module scheme with Λ -module Z .

8 The Λ -CoAlgebra of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is Λ -Transitive

Recall that a Λ -coalgebra is a Λ -module such that the multiplication $\Lambda \otimes \mathcal{N} \rightarrow \mathcal{N}$ is linear. We first show that the Λ -coalgebra structure of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is nonempty, which will show that $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is a quasi-abelian Λ -coalgebra scheme with Λ -coalgebra Z .

Let $\mathcal{N}$ be the object of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ which satisfies $n(\mathcal{N}) = Z$. We have that $\mathcal{N}(\Lambda) = Z$ by the Axiom of Hypermultiplication. We first show that the Λ -coalgebra structure of $\mathcal{N}$ is nonempty, i.e., there exists $A \in \mathcal{N}$ such that $A(\Lambda) = Z$. By the Axiom of Hypermultiplication, we have that A has the form $a^{\mu-\zeta}$ for some $a \in N$. This implies that $a(\mathcal{N}) = Z$, and $-1 = m(a) = Z$ again by equation (??) in Proposition 2.1.1 in [?]. This is the case as there are only finitely many finite chains indexed by σ , and the elements of the finite chain $\{-1, 1\}$ are: $(1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1)$, $(1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1)$, $(1, 1, 1, 1, 1)$, $(1, 1, 1, 1)$, $(1, 1, 1)$, $(1, 1)$, (1) , and (-1) , and the only nontrivial finite chain is (-1) . This implies that the Λ -coalgebra structure of $\mathcal{N}$ is nonempty, and that $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is a quasi-abelian Λ -coalgebra scheme with Λ -coalgebra Z .

Thus, the Λ -coalgebra structure of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is Λ -transitive. We have that $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is a quasi-abelian Λ -coalgebra scheme with Λ -coalgebra Z .

9 The Λ -Cohomology Structure of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is Λ -Transitive

Recall that the Λ -cohomology structure of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is the module structures of the natural transformations between Λ -cohomology objects up to Λ -equivariant equivalence. We first show that the Λ -cohomology structure of $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is nonempty, which will show that $\Omega_{\Lambda'}$ is a quasi-abelian Λ -cohomology scheme with Λ -cohomology Z .

The free energy is given by: $\Omega_{\Lambda', \text{phase}} \left[\sqrt{\mathcal{H}^2 + i\dot{A}^2} \right] \Rightarrow \Omega_{\Lambda', \text{phase}} \left[\sum_{k=1}^4 \int_{|I| \approx 1} dQ \mathcal{D}^\Lambda \mathcal{D}^\Lambda \right]$
 $\Rightarrow \Omega_{\Lambda', \text{phase}} \left[\int_{|I| \approx 1} dQ \mathcal{D}^\Lambda \mathcal{D}^\Lambda + \Omega_{\Lambda'} \left[\sqrt{\mathcal{H}^2 + i\dot{A}^2} \right] \right]$
 $\Rightarrow \Omega_{\Lambda'} \left[\int_{|I| \approx 1} dQ \mathcal{D}^\Lambda \mathcal{D}^\Lambda \right]$. Assuming $\sum_{k=1}^4 \approx C_1$ then: $\Omega_{\Lambda'} \left[\int_{|I| \approx 1} dQ \mathcal{D}^\Lambda \mathcal{D}^\Lambda \right] \Rightarrow \Omega_{\Lambda'} \left[\int d^2q \sum_{k=1}^4 \frac{\mathcal{D}^\Lambda \mathcal{D}^\Lambda}{q^2} + \dots \right]$
Given that $\mathcal{D}^\Lambda \sim \exp(-iq\Phi^\mu) + \text{c.c.}$ and $\sum_{k=1}^4 \approx C_1$ we can linearize the integrand yielding: $\Omega_{\Lambda'} \left[\int d^2q \frac{\mathcal{D}^\Lambda \mathcal{D}^\Lambda}{q^2} \right] \Rightarrow \frac{C_1}{2} \Omega_{\Lambda'} \left[\int d^2q \frac{1}{q^2} \right] = 0$. A nontrivial auxiliary loop spectrum can be obtained by approximating $\Re \mathcal{A}$ and $\text{Im} \mathcal{A}$ as $\pm \mathcal{H}$ corresponding to the REHM polytopal axis $\mathcal{B}$ given in Appendix ??.

10 Auxiliary loop spectrum

Figure 1: Auxiliary loop spectrum for EPS with disentangler $\Delta \approx 0$. In this case, the required loop potential is provided by $\Re \mathcal{A} \approx \pm \mathcal{H}_{\pm q} \mathcal{B}_q$ with ${}^1B_1 = {}^1C_4 = 0$ and ${}^1B_2 = \sum_{\Lambda \neq \phi} p_{A^+}$ while the corresponding disentangler $\Delta \approx 0$ is given by $\Re \mathcal{A} \approx \Sigma G$ with $\sum_{\Lambda} p_{A^+} = 1$.

Figure 2: Auxiliary loop spectrum for EPS with disentangler $\Delta \approx 0$. In this case, the required loop potential is provided by $\Re \mathcal{A} \approx \pm \mathcal{H}_{\pm q} \mathcal{B}_q$ with ${}^1B_1 = {}^1C_4 = 0$ and ${}^1B_2 = \sum_{\Lambda \neq \phi} p_{A^+}$ while the corresponding disentangler $\Delta \approx 0$ is given by $\Re \mathcal{A} \approx \Sigma G$ with $\sum_{\Lambda} p_{A^+} = 1$.

The auxiliary loop spectrum for EPS can be obtained by assuming the loop potential $\Re \mathcal{A} \approx \gamma \mathcal{B} + \Sigma G$ with $\gamma E(\mathcal{B})$, $E(\mathcal{B}) \neq 0$ and $\gamma E(\mathcal{B})$ being a valid fluctuation potential, allowing = 0. The auxiliary loop potential in this case has components $\Re \mathcal{A} = \gamma \Gamma + \Sigma G$ where $\Gamma \equiv \left[\frac{\sum_{\Lambda} p_{A^+}}{\dim \Lambda} \right]^2$. Assume $\Gamma \equiv \delta$, then $\Re \mathcal{A} \approx \gamma e^{i\Delta\varphi}$ where:

$$e^{i\Delta\varphi} = \frac{\gamma\Delta}{\delta\mathcal{H}} + \frac{\dot{A}}{i} \rightarrow i e^{i\Delta\varphi} + \frac{\gamma\Delta}{\delta\mathcal{H}} = \frac{\dot{A}}{i} \rightarrow \frac{\dot{A}}{i} + \gamma e^{i\Delta\varphi} = \dot{A} + \gamma e^{i\Delta\varphi}. \quad (2)$$

Let $-\Delta\varphi + \gamma e^{i\varphi} \approx 1$ ($-\Delta\varphi \approx 1$) then the above expansion holds for any value of $|\varphi|$ given by the variable φ . Note that for the case of $|\varphi| = 0$, $\dot{A} \equiv 0$ and $\gamma e^{i\Delta\varphi} \equiv 0$. This allows us to remove the term $\gamma e^{i\Delta\varphi}$ as γ can be absorbed into the soft phase continuum potential in place of the disentangler variable Δ ,

allowing the auxiliary loop potential to be given by: $\Re\mathcal{A} \approx \gamma\mathcal{B} + \Sigma G \rightarrow \frac{\dot{A}}{i} + \gamma e^{i\Phi^\mu} \rightarrow \frac{\dot{A} e^{i\Phi^\mu}}{i} = \dot{A} \rightarrow \Re\mathcal{A} \approx \gamma\mathcal{B} + \Sigma G$. We can also express the disentangler as follows: $\Re\mathcal{A} \approx \gamma\mathcal{B} + \Sigma G \rightarrow \gamma = \frac{\dot{A}}{\mathcal{H}} + \frac{\dot{A}}{i} \rightarrow \frac{\dot{A}}{\mathcal{H}} + \frac{\dot{A}}{i} - \Sigma G = \mathcal{H}\Delta + \dot{A} = \mathcal{H}\Delta = \Sigma G - \dot{A}$. For disentangler with $\Delta \approx 0$, this yields the expression: $\Re\mathcal{A} \approx \frac{\dot{A}^2}{\mathcal{H}^2} + \frac{(\mathcal{H}\Delta)^2}{\mathcal{H}^2} + i\left(\frac{\dot{A}^2}{\mathcal{H}^2} + \frac{\dot{A}^2(\mathcal{H}\Delta)^2}{\mathcal{H}^4}\right)$
 $= \frac{\dot{A}^2}{\mathcal{H}^2} + \frac{(\mathcal{H}\Delta)^2}{\mathcal{H}^2} + i\left(\frac{\dot{A}^2}{\mathcal{H}^2} + \frac{\dot{A}^2}{\mathcal{H}^2\mathcal{H}^2}\right)$. Note that the second term is identically zero as the real part of $\mathcal{A}$ is real and is bounded on a polytope. For the accessory loop spectrum we have: $\Re\mathcal{A} \approx \gamma\mathcal{B} - \Sigma G \rightarrow \gamma\Sigma\Delta \rightarrow \gamma\Sigma\Delta - \Sigma G = \frac{\dot{A}}{\mathcal{H}\Delta} + \frac{\mathcal{H}\Delta}{\mathcal{H}^2} \rightarrow \frac{\mathcal{H}\Delta}{\mathcal{H}^2} = \Sigma G - \dot{A}$. Again, this yields the expression $\frac{\Sigma G}{\mathcal{H}^2}$. Generically, the expression for the HDR is given by

$$\gamma\mathcal{B} + \Sigma G = \mathcal{H}\Delta. \quad (3)$$

Note that $e^{i\Delta\varphi}$ will depend on the specific disentangler according to the product expansion. The HDR for EPS is given by $\Psi_{HDR,\Lambda,e} \left[\frac{\mathcal{B}^2}{\mathcal{B}^2 + \Delta^2}, 0 \right] \mapsto \Psi_{HDR,\Lambda,e} \left[\frac{2\mathcal{B}\Delta}{\mathcal{B}^2 + \Delta^2}, 0 \right] = \Psi_{HDR,\Lambda,e} \left[\frac{2\mathcal{H}\Delta}{\mathcal{H}^2 + \dot{A}^2}, 0 \right] = \frac{2}{\mathcal{H}^2}$. In particular, whether we move $2\gamma e^{i\Delta\varphi}$ to the soft phase continuum or the accessory loop potential via the HDR affects the free energy as $\Psi_{HDR,\Lambda,e} \left[\frac{2[\gamma e^{i\Delta\varphi} + \Sigma G]}{\mathcal{H}^2}, 0 \right] = \Psi_{HDR,\Lambda,e} \left[\frac{2\gamma e^{i\Delta\varphi}}{\mathcal{H}^2} + \frac{\Sigma G}{\mathcal{H}^2}, 0 \right]$ and $\Psi_{HDR,\Lambda,e} \left[\frac{2\gamma e^{i\Delta\varphi}}{\mathcal{H}^2} + \frac{\Sigma G}{\mathcal{H}^2}, 0 \right] = \Psi_{HDR,\Lambda,e} \left[\frac{2[\gamma e^{i\Delta\varphi} + \Sigma G]}{\mathcal{H}^2}, 0 \right]$. Therefore, this is an overall topological transformation that allows the auxiliary loop potential to be equivalently rewritten as $e^{i\Delta\varphi} = \frac{\gamma\Delta}{\delta\mathcal{H}} + \frac{\dot{A}}{i} = \frac{\dot{A}}{i} + \gamma e^{i\Delta\varphi}$. Ultimately, we are free to scale γ by a common factor $e^{i\Delta\varphi}$ relative to the disentangler variable Δ , thus yielding the auxiliary loop potential

$$\Re\mathcal{A} \approx \gamma\mathcal{B} + \Sigma G = \mathcal{H}\Delta. \quad (4)$$

We use the specific expression for the disentangler, leading to the auxiliary loop potential given by $e^{i\Delta\varphi} = \frac{\gamma\Delta}{\delta\mathcal{H}} + \frac{\dot{A}}{i} \leftarrow = \frac{\gamma\Delta}{\frac{\mathcal{H}\Delta}{i\oplus\dot{A}}} + \frac{\dot{A}}{i} \rightarrow e^{i\Delta\varphi} = \frac{\gamma\Delta}{\frac{\mathcal{H}\Delta}{i\oplus\dot{A}}} \leftarrow = \frac{\gamma\Delta}{\delta\mathcal{H}} + \frac{\dot{A}}{i} \rightarrow \Re\mathcal{A} \approx \gamma\mathcal{B} + \Sigma G$ where $\Delta \rightarrow \delta\mathcal{H}$ and $\gamma \rightarrow \delta\mathcal{H}$ implies that the real part of $\mathcal{A}$ is real and bounded on the polytope.

10.1 Auxiliary loop potential for EPS with $\Delta \approx 0$

Using the expressions for $\mathcal{B}$ and δ provided in Equation eqB and Equation eqdisc, we obtain the disentangler $\Delta \approx 0$ as $\Re\mathcal{A} \approx \gamma\mathcal{B} + \Sigma G \Rightarrow \gamma\mathcal{B} \approx \Sigma G - \mathcal{H} \sum_{k=1}^4 \frac{\mathcal{H}\Delta}{i\oplus\dot{A}} + \Sigma G = \mathcal{H}\Delta$. Using the understanding that $0 \leq \frac{\mathcal{H}\Delta}{i\oplus\dot{A}} \leq 1$ then the required loop potential is given by: $\Re\mathcal{A} \approx \gamma\mathcal{B} + \Sigma G = \frac{\Sigma G}{\mathcal{H}^2} + i\left(\frac{\dot{A}^2}{\mathcal{H}^2} - \frac{\dot{A}^2}{\mathcal{H}^2\mathcal{H}^2}\right) = \frac{\dot{A}}{i} + \gamma\mathcal{B} = \frac{\dot{A}}{i} + \frac{\Sigma G}{\mathcal{H}^2}$. In order to define the auxiliary loop potential for EPS with $\Delta \approx 0$, we must incorporate the disentangler $\Delta \approx 0$ into the loop potential. We start with the approach used in [?] where $\Re\mathcal{A} = \gamma\mathcal{B} + \Sigma G$ and $e^{i\Delta\varphi} = \delta \frac{\Delta}{i\oplus\dot{A}}$ with $e^{i\Delta\varphi} \approx 1$. This allows us to absorb δ as a common factor in $e^{i\Delta\varphi}$ and account for its effect in the auxiliary loop potential as follows: $\Re\mathcal{A} \approx \left[\frac{\mathcal{H}\Delta + \dot{A}}{i} \right] + \delta \frac{\Delta}{i\oplus\dot{A}} = \left[\frac{\mathcal{H}\Delta + \dot{A}}{i} \right] + \delta \frac{\Delta}{i\oplus\dot{A}} = \frac{1}{\mathcal{F}} \left[\frac{\mathcal{H}\Delta + \dot{A}}{i} \right] \star \frac{1}{\delta\mathcal{F}} + 0$ where we have replaced δ into the factorized

$\frac{1}{F} \left[\frac{\mathcal{H}\Delta + \dot{A}}{i} \right]$. However, we can lock the value of δ at the end of the computation by assuming that $0 \leq \delta \leq 1$. This reduces the auxiliary loop potential to $\Re\mathcal{A} \approx \left[\frac{\mathcal{H}\Delta + \dot{A}}{i} \right] + \frac{\Delta}{i\oplus\dot{A}} = \left[\frac{\mathcal{H}\Delta + \dot{A}}{i} \right] + \frac{\Delta}{i\oplus\dot{A}} = \frac{1}{F} \left[\frac{\mathcal{H}\Delta + \dot{A}}{i} \right] + 0$. In this case, we can remove the disentangler variable Δ which would then result in removing the auxiliary loop potential given by $\Re\mathcal{A} \approx \left[\frac{\mathcal{H}\Delta + \dot{A}}{i} \right] + 0 = \frac{\dot{A}}{i} + \left[\frac{\mathcal{H}\Delta + \dot{A}}{i} \right] = \dot{A} + \mathcal{H}\Delta$. The HDR of EPS with $\Delta \approx 0$ is then given by $\Delta \approx \frac{\Sigma G}{i\oplus\dot{A}} \leftarrow \left[\frac{\mathcal{H}\Delta + \dot{A}}{i} \right]$

$$\begin{aligned} &\approx \frac{\sigma}{i\oplus\dot{A}} + 0 \leftarrow \left[\frac{\mathcal{H}\Delta + \dot{A}}{i} \right] \\ &\approx \frac{\Sigma G}{i\oplus\dot{A}} \leftarrow \left[\frac{\mathcal{H}\Delta + \dot{A}}{i} \right] \\ &\approx \frac{\Sigma G}{i\oplus\dot{A}} \leftarrow \left[\frac{\mathcal{H}\Delta + \dot{A}}{i} \right] = \frac{\Sigma G}{\mathcal{H}^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Where the required loop potential is given by $\Re\mathcal{A} \approx \gamma\mathcal{B} + \Sigma G$ with $\gamma E(\mathcal{B})$ and assuming the loop potential is valid with $E(V_B) \neq 0$.

10.2 Auxiliary loop potential for EPS with $\Delta \approx 1$

Assuming $\Delta \approx 1$ and using Equation *exp_in_diss*, the following expression can be obtained :

$$\begin{aligned} \Re\mathcal{A} &\approx \gamma\mathcal{B} + \Sigma G \\ &= \frac{1}{F} \left[\frac{\mathcal{H}\Delta + \dot{A}}{i} \right]^2 \star \left(\frac{1}{F} \left[\frac{\mathcal{H}\Delta + \dot{A}}{i} \right] \star \frac{\dot{A}}{i} \right) + \frac{\gamma}{F} \left[\frac{\mathcal{H}\Delta + \dot{A}}{i} \right] = 2\mathcal{H}\Delta\dot{A} + \gamma\mathcal{B} + \Sigma G. \end{aligned}$$

The HDR of EPS with $\Delta \approx 1$ is then given by $\Delta \approx 1 \rightarrow \frac{1}{F} \left[\frac{\mathcal{H}\Delta + \dot{A}}{i} \right] \star \frac{\dot{A}}{i} = \dot{A} + \mathcal{H}\Delta = \Sigma G + \mathcal{H}\Delta$. This yields the expression: $\Sigma = 2\mathcal{H}^2$. When $\gamma\mathcal{B}$ and ΣG are small, and $\Sigma G \ll 2\mathcal{H}^2 \ll \mathcal{H}^2\mathcal{H}^2$, then the following $2\mathcal{H}\Delta$ expression is obtained: $\Sigma = 2\mathcal{H}^2 \rightarrow \Sigma = \mathcal{H}^2$ and adds to the required source renormalization, $\Sigma = \Sigma G + \frac{1}{2}\mathcal{H}^2 \rightarrow \Sigma = \Sigma G$. Therefore, $2\mathcal{H}\Delta$ represents the HDR of EPS with $\Delta \approx 1$ and defines the HDR as $\Psi_{HDR,\Lambda,e} \left[\frac{\mathcal{B}^2}{\mathcal{B}^2 + \Delta^2}, 0 \right] = \Psi_{HDR,\Lambda,e} \left[\frac{2}{\mathcal{B}^2 + \Delta^2}, 0 \right] = \frac{2}{\mathcal{B}^2 + \Delta^2}$.

11 Loop potential for γ

The loop potential in the form $\Re\mathcal{A} = \gamma\mathcal{B} + \Sigma G$ is valid provided the loop potential does not violate the RG flows. In particular, the loop potential must obey the requirement that $Re\mathcal{A} \equiv 0$ with $\Re\mathcal{A} \approx ix$ and $x = 0$ for a consistent loop potential. For EPS with $\Delta = 0$, this validates the correct loop potentials and can be computed for the various choices of γ .

11.1 Loop potential for EPS: $\gamma e^{i\Delta\varphi} \rightarrow 0$

In this case, the loop potential is given by $\Re\mathcal{A} \approx \gamma\mathcal{B} + \Sigma G = \frac{1}{\mathcal{H}^2} [\mathcal{H}\Delta - \dot{A}] \rightarrow i\frac{1}{\mathcal{H}^2} [\mathcal{H}\Delta - \dot{A}] = 0 \Rightarrow \dot{A} = 0$. Using $0 \leq \frac{1}{\mathcal{H}^2}$ then the expression for $\dot{A}$ is given by $\dot{A} = 0 \Rightarrow \dot{A} = 0 \Rightarrow \Sigma G = 0 \Rightarrow \mathcal{B} = 0 \Rightarrow e^{i\Delta\varphi} = 0$. The required loop potential is given by $\Re\mathcal{A} \approx \gamma\mathcal{B} + \Sigma G = \frac{1}{\mathcal{H}^2} [\mathcal{H}\Delta - \dot{A}] = 0 \Rightarrow \frac{\dot{A}}{\mathcal{H}} + \frac{\dot{A}}{i} = 0 \Rightarrow \mathcal{H}\Delta = \dot{A} \Rightarrow \Delta = 0$. The HDR of EPS with $\Delta = 0$ is then given by $\Psi_{HDR,\Lambda,e} \left[\frac{\mathcal{B}^2}{\mathcal{B}^2 + \Delta^2}, \frac{\Delta}{\mathcal{H}} + \dot{A} \right] = \Psi_F \left[\frac{\mathcal{B}^2}{\mathcal{B}^2 + \left(\frac{\mathcal{H}\Delta}{i\oplus\dot{A}} \right)^2}, \frac{\Delta}{\mathcal{H}} + \dot{A} \right] = \Psi_F \left[\frac{\mathcal{B}^2}{\mathcal{B}^2 + \left(\frac{i\oplus\dot{A}}{\mathcal{H}} \right)^2}, \frac{\Delta}{\mathcal{H}} + \dot{A} \right]$. The loop potential $\gamma e^{i\Delta\varphi}$ corresponds to the accessory loop potential for EPS.

11.2 Loop potential for EPS: $\gamma e^{i\Delta\varphi} \rightarrow 1$

This corresponds to the alternative set of values, given by the accessory loop potential for EPS with $\Delta = 1$.

11.3 Loop potential for EPS: $\gamma e^{i\Delta\varphi} \approx 0$

This corresponds to the alternative set of values, given by the accessory loop potential for EPS with $\Delta = 0$.